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Latest results from the NA62 experiment at CERN:
precision measurements and searches in beam-dump mode

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Abstract

The latest results from the NA62 experiment at CERN on precision measurements and searches in beam-dump mode are presented. The precision measurements of the following charged kaon decay channels are performed on data collected in 2017-2018: $K^+ \rightarrow \pi^0 e^+ \nu \gamma$, $K^+ \rightarrow \pi^+ \mu^+ \mu^-$, $K^+ \rightarrow \pi^+ \gamma \gamma$. The data collected in beam-dump mode in 2021 are used to search for dark photon decaying into charged lepton pairs: $A' \rightarrow \mu^+ \mu^-$, $A' \rightarrow e^+ e^-$.

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1 The NA62 experiment

The NA62 experiment at CERN is designed to measure the $K^+ \rightarrow \pi^+ \nu \bar{\nu}$ branching fraction [1]; the beam and the detector are described in [2]. More recent details about the performance of the NA62 detectors are available in [3, 4].

Thanks to auxiliary trigger lines [5, 6], the NA62 physics program comprises most of the K^+ decay channels, including the possibility of precisely measuring decays as $K^+ \rightarrow \pi^0 e^+ \nu \gamma$, $K^+ \rightarrow \pi^+ \mu^+ \mu^-$, $K^+ \rightarrow \pi^+ \gamma \gamma$.

Specific data taking periods are operated in beam-dump mode, allowing to search for the production of feebly interacting dark photons, then decaying into charged lepton pairs: $A' \rightarrow \mu^+ \mu^-$, $A' \rightarrow e^+ e^-$.

Other recent NA62 results are published in [7, 8, 9].

2 The $K^+ \rightarrow \pi^0 e^+ \nu \gamma$ decay

The radiative decay $K^+ \rightarrow \pi^0 e^+ \nu \gamma$ is defined as a subset of the inclusive decays $K^+ \rightarrow \pi^0 e^+ \nu(\gamma)$ that requires a minimum photon energy (E_γ) and a range of angles between the positron and the radiative photon ($\theta_{e\gamma}$) in the kaon rest frame. The definitions of the three kinematic regions used in this analysis are given in Table 1, together with theoretical and experimental results for the ratios R_j of the branching fractions of the radiative decay $K^+ \rightarrow \pi^0 e^+ \nu \gamma$ to the inclusive decay $K^+ \rightarrow \pi^0 e^+ \nu(\gamma)$.

Table 1: Definition of kinematic regions, R_j expectations from ChPT $\mathcal{O}(p^6)$ calculations [10] and measurements from ISTRAP+ [11] and OKA [12] experiments, with statistical and systematic uncertainties quoted separately.

	$E_\gamma, \theta_{e\gamma}$ conditions	ChPT	ISTRAP+	OKA
$R_1 \times 10^2$	$E_\gamma > 10$ MeV, $\theta_{e\gamma} > 10^\circ$	1.804 ± 0.021	$1.81 \pm 0.03 \pm 0.07$	$1.990 \pm 0.017 \pm 0.021$
$R_2 \times 10^2$	$E_\gamma > 30$ MeV, $\theta_{e\gamma} > 20^\circ$	0.640 ± 0.008	$0.63 \pm 0.02 \pm 0.03$	$0.587 \pm 0.010 \pm 0.015$
$R_3 \times 10^2$	$E_\gamma > 10$ MeV, $0.6 < \cos \theta_{e\gamma} < 0.9$	0.559 ± 0.006	$0.47 \pm 0.02 \pm 0.03$	$0.532 \pm 0.010 \pm 0.012$

The amplitude of the $K_{e3\gamma}$ decay is sensitive to T-violating contributions, which can be studied with the dimensionless T-odd observable ξ and the corresponding T-asymmetry A_ξ , defined as:

$$\xi = \frac{\vec{p}_\gamma \cdot (\vec{p}_e \times \vec{p}_\pi)}{(M_K \cdot c)^3}, \quad A_\xi = \frac{N_+ - N_-}{N_+ + N_-}, \quad (1)$$

where \vec{p} is the three-momentum of each particle in the kaon rest frame and N_+ (N_-) is the number of events with positive (negative) values of ξ . The uncertainty of the most precise published A_ξ measurement [13] is larger than the range of theoretical expectations.

A sample of 1.3×10^5 $K^+ \rightarrow \pi^0 e^+ \nu \gamma$ candidates with less than 1% background was collected by the NA62 experiment at the CERN SPS in 2017–2018, and a measurement of the ratios R_j and the T-asymmetry A_ξ was performed. The details of the analysis and the results are provided in [14]. The measured ratios, $R_1 = (1.715 \pm 0.011) \times 10^{-2}$, $R_2 = (0.609 \pm 0.006) \times 10^{-2}$, $R_3 = (0.533 \pm 0.004) \times 10^{-2}$, are at least a factor of two more precise than previous measurements. The relative uncertainties do not exceed 1%, matching the precision of the most accurate theoretical calculations. The T-asymmetry measurements performed in the same kinematic regions, $A_\xi(R_1) = (-1.2 \pm 2.8_{\text{stat}} \pm 1.9_{\text{syst}}) \times 10^{-3}$, $A_\xi(R_2) = (-3.4 \pm 4.3_{\text{stat}} \pm 3.0_{\text{syst}}) \times 10^{-3}$, $A_\xi(R_3) = (-9.1 \pm 5.1_{\text{stat}} \pm 3.5_{\text{syst}}) \times 10^{-3}$, show

an improved precision and are compatible with absence of asymmetry. Their uncertainties remain larger than the theoretical expectations.

3 The $K^+ \rightarrow \pi^+ \mu^+ \mu^-$ decay

A sample of 2.8×10^4 $K^+ \rightarrow \pi^+ \mu^+ \mu^-$ candidates with negligible background was collected by the NA62 experiment at the CERN SPS in 2017–2018. The details of the analysis and the results are provided in [15]. The model independent branching fraction is measured to be $(9.15 \pm 0.08) \times 10^{-8}$, with a precision improved by a factor of three with respect to the previous measurements. The precision is limited by the statistics of the selected signal sample. The decay form factor is presented as a function of the squared dimuon mass. A measurement of the form factor parameters and their uncertainties is performed using a description based on Chiral Perturbation Theory at $\mathcal{O}(p^6)$: $a_+ = -0.575 \pm 0.013$, $b_+ = -0.722 \pm 0.043$. The present measurement is the first to employ inclusive radiative corrections in the simulation of the signal channel. The form factor parameters are consistent with those formerly measured, as well as with the results obtained in the electron mode by other experiments, suggesting agreement with lepton flavour universality in the $K^+ \rightarrow \pi^+ l^+ l^-$ ($l = e, \mu$) decays.

4 The $K^+ \rightarrow \pi^+ \gamma \gamma$ decay

The $K^+ \rightarrow \pi^+ \gamma \gamma$ decay is described in the Chiral Perturbation Theory as a function of several low energy parameters known from other kaon decay modes, plus one, named \hat{c} , specific of this decay mode, and it is dominated by long distance physics effects [16]. The main kinematic variable is the di-photon mass. NA62 has performed the analysis of the $K^+ \rightarrow \pi^+ \gamma \gamma$ decay using the data collected in 2016–2018, where about 4×10^3 signal candidates have been selected. This is the largest world sample to date, with a relative background contamination smaller than 10%. The details of the analysis and the preliminary results have been presented for the first time in September 2022 [17], and a publication with the final result is in preparation.

A fit to the di-photon mass spectrum using the ChPT $\mathcal{O}(p^6)$ description allows the extraction of \hat{c} , which represents a test ground for the Chiral Perturbation Theory. The background is extracted from simulation and validated with data in suitable control regions orthogonal to the signal. A model independent branching fraction is also measured, normalized to the $K^+ \rightarrow \pi^+ \pi^0$ decay. The preliminary result of the \hat{c} measurement is $1.713 \pm 0.075 \pm 0.037$, while the branching fraction is measured to be $(9.73 \pm 0.17 \pm 0.08) \times 10^{-7}$. The results are consistent, albeit significantly more precise than previous measurements.

5 Dark photon searches in beam-dump mode

NA62 also collected data in beam-dump mode. In this configuration, dark photons may be produced by protons dumped on an absorber and reach a decay volume beginning 80 m downstream.

A search for dark photons decaying in flight to $\mu^+ \mu^-$ pairs has been performed, based on a sample of 1.4×10^{17} protons on dump collected in 2021 [18]. With a counting experiment through a cut-based and blind analysis, one event is found, with a possible interpretation as a combinatorial background. No evidence of a dark photon signal is established. A region of the dark photon parameter space (coupling constant, mass) is excluded at 90% CL, extending the limits of previous experiments

in the mass range 215–550 MeV/ c^2 for coupling constants of the order of 10^{-6} . In addition, the result is interpreted in terms of the emission of axion-like particles in a model-independent approach. The result is found to improve on previous limits for masses below 280 MeV/ c^2 .

A similar search has been performed for dark photons decaying into e^+e^- pairs, without any signal candidate observed. The details of this analysis and the preliminary results have been presented for the first time in March 2023 [19], and a publication with the final result is in preparation. The exclusion limits are combined with the ones obtained from the di-muon channel, and extend the limits provided by previous experiment for dark photon mass above 20 MeV/ c^2 .

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